

SUSTAINABLE APPROACH FOR CORROSION CONTROL IN ACIDIC MEDIA

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ABSTRACT: Mass loss method and thermometric methods have been employed to study the corrosion inhibition of Mild steel in acidic media (HCl). Three Schiff's bases viz; N(vanillidine)-4-methyl-1-phenylimine(SB₁), N(vanillidine)-4-methoxy-1-phenylimine(SB₂), N(anisidine)-1-naphthylimine(SB₃). Values of inhibition efficiency obtained from two methods are in good agreement and dependent upon the concentration from the mass loss data, it is concluded that the inhibition efficiency increases with the increase in concentration of inhibitor.

Key words: corrosion inhibition, weight loss method, thermometric method, mild steel correlation.

INTRODUCTION:

Mild steel is an important metal regarding to its wide applications in industry in various mechanical and structural purposes. It is widely used in engineering fabrications like bridgework, buildings, steam engine parts automobiles, for ship hulls and off shore drilling platform etc.

However, mild steel when left open, the surroundings tend to corrode, the corrosion of mild steel in atmosphere is affected by various factors like humidity [1], metal composition, temperature, presence of pollutants like sulphur dioxide [2], for buried structure, the amount of moisture, type of soil [3], etc. influence the corrosion rate and therefore the life of the material is adversely affected. The acid solutions especially hydrochloric acid, sulphuric acid and mixture of both acids are constantly involved in pickling, industrial cleaning and rescaling. During pickling of metal hot acid solutions are used [4]. The acid solution corrode the metal surface leading to a great economic loss. This has invited attention of many chemical researchers.

The protection of metal from deterioration against corrosion without damaging the metal surface is by using inhibitors [5-6]

Mild steel is passive towards an alkali but it is prone to corrosion in acids like hydrochloric acid, sulphuric acid and mixture of both acids.

Generally heterocyclic compounds containing heteroatom nitrogen, oxygen and sulphur offer effective corrosion resistance by getting adsorbed on the metal surface through the lone pair of electrons present on these atoms. This process may block the active site and hence decreases the corrosion rate. The efficiency of heterocyclic compounds depends upon the electron density of heteroatom [7-9].

Schiff's bases act as a corrosion inhibitors for mild steel, when the concentrations of the inhibitors were increased the inhibition efficiencies increase with increasing surface coverage [10-15].

In the present study three novel nitrogen containing ligands (Schiff's bases) viz N(vanillidine)-4-methyl-1-phenylimine(SB₁), N(vanillidine)-4-methoxy-1-phenylimine(SB₂), N(anisidine)-1-naphthylimine(SB₃) has been tested for their corrosion inhibitive properties for mild steel in various concentrations 0.1, 0.5, 1.0, 2.0N of hydrochloric acid by employing mass loss and thermometric method.

EXPERIMENTAL

Rectangular specimens of mild steel of size 2.5x1.5x0.02 cm containing a small hole of (~) 3mm diameter near the upper edge were employed for the determination of corrosion rate. The specimens were well cleaned by buffing to produce a mirror finish with the help of emery paper and were then degreased. Solutions of HCl were prepared using double distilled water. All chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade. Different Schiff's bases were synthesized by conventional methods. Each specimen was suspended by a glass hook and immersed in a beaker containing 50 ml. of test solutions at room temperature and left exposed to air. After definite times of exposure, the specimens were taken out, washed thoroughly with benzene and then dried with hot air dryer, than the final mass loss of each specimen was taken and the loss in mass was calculated. The percentage inhibition efficiency ($\eta\%$) of inhibitors were calculated using the following formula.

$$\eta\% = \frac{100(\Delta M_u - \Delta M_i)}{\Delta M_u}$$

Where ΔM_u = Mass loss of the metal in uninhibited solution

ΔM_i = Mass loss of the metal in inhibited solution

Corrosion rate is determined from the mass loss as follows

$$\text{Corrosion Rate (mmpy)} = \frac{\text{Mass loss} \times 87.6}{\text{Area} \times \text{Time} \times \text{Metal density}}$$

Where ΔM is the loss of mass in mg. A is the area of the specimen in square cm, D is the density of metal in g/cm^3 and T is the time in hours.

The degree of surface coverage (θ) can be calculated as fol

$$\text{Surface Coverage } (\theta) = \frac{\Delta M_u - \Delta M_i}{\Delta M_u}$$

Where ΔM_u is the mass loss in uninhibited solution and ΔM_i is the mass loss in inhibited solution.

Thermometric measurement

Inhibition efficiencies were also determined by thermometric method. In this method, the variation of temperature is followed as a function of time. The specimens of size 2.50 x 1.55 x 0.02 cm were immersed in 50mL of acid solution in a thermally insulated chamber. The tests were carried out in different concentrations of acids solutions. The inhibition studies were carried out in 0.12%, 0.24%, 0.36%, 0.48%, and 0.60% of some novel nitrogen containing ligands (Schiff's bases). The results were used to calculate Reaction Number (RN) and inhibition efficiency ($\eta\%$)

Reaction Number can be calculated by the following equation-

$$\text{RN} = (T_m - T_i) / t$$

Where T_m and T_i are the maximum and initial temperature respectively and t is the time required to reach the maximum temperature in minutes.

The inhibition efficiency can be calculated as-

$$\eta\% = 100 (RN_f - RN_i) / RN_f$$

Where RN_f and RN_i are the reaction numbers in blank (free) and in inhibited solution system respectively.

After calculating the percentage inhibitions efficiency ($\eta\%$), we'll calculate the coefficient of correlations (r) between the inhibitions additions and percentage inhibition efficiency by using the fact.

$$r = \frac{N\sum dxdy - (\sum dx)(\sum dy)}{\sqrt{N\sum dx^2 - (\sum dx)^2} \sqrt{N\sum dy^2 - (\sum dy)^2}}$$

Table – 1: Corrosion data for different concentrations of Schiff's bases for mild steel in 2.0 N HCl at 298 ± 0.1 K.Area of exposure – 7.75 cm²

Time of exposure 19 hrs

x (inhibitor addition)	ΔM (mg)	η% (y)	dx = $x - \bar{x}$	dy = $y - \bar{y}$	dx^2 = $(x - \bar{x})^2$	dy^2 = $(y - \bar{y})^2$	$dxdy$ = $(x - \bar{x})(y - \bar{y})$
Uninhibited SB ₁	1063	–	–	–	–	–	–
0.12%	441	58.51	-.24	-20.018	.0576	400.720324	4.80432
0.24%	371	65.09	-.12	-13.438	.0144	180.579844	1.61256
0.36%	134	87.39	0	8.862	0	78.535044	0
0.48%	114	89.27	.12	10.742	.0144	115.390564	1.28904
0.60%	81	92.38	.24	13.852	.0576	191.877904	3.32448
Total			0	0	0.144	967.103672	11.0304

Here,

$$\bar{x} = .36,$$

$$\bar{y} = 78.528$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 r &= \frac{5 \times 11.0304 - 0}{\sqrt{5 \times 0.144} \sqrt{5 \times 967.103672 - 0}} \\
 &= \frac{55.152}{59.00485777} \\
 &= .934702702 \\
 &\cong .93
 \end{aligned}$$

Table – 2: Corrosion data for different concentrations of Schiff's bases for mild steel in 2.0 N HCl at 298 ± 0.1 K.Area of exposure – 7.75 cm²

Time of exposure 19 hrs

x (inhibitor addition)	ΔM (mg)	η% (y)	dx $= x - \bar{x}$	dy $= y - \bar{y}$	dx^2 $= (x - \bar{x})^2$	dy^2 $= (y - \bar{y})^2$	$dx dy$ $= (x - \bar{x})(y - \bar{y})$
Uninhibited SB ₂	1063	-	-	-	-	-	-
0.12%	88	91.72	-.24	-1.394	.0576	1.943236	0.33456
0.24%	84	92.09	-.12	-1.024	.0144	1.048576	0.12288
0.36%	70	93.34	0	0.226	0	0.051076	0
0.48%	65	93.88	.12	0.766	.0144	0.586756	0.09192
0.60%	58	94.54	.24	1.426	.0576	2.033476	0.34224
Total			0	0	.1440	5.66312	0.8916

Here, $\bar{x} = .36$, $\bar{y} = 88.602$

$$\begin{aligned}
 r &= \frac{5 \times 0.8916 - 0}{\sqrt{5 \times 0.144} \sqrt{5 \times 5.66312 - 0}} \\
 &= \frac{4.458}{5.321240457} \\
 &= 0.98732681 \\
 &\cong .99
 \end{aligned}$$

Table – 3: Corrosion data for different concentrations of Schiff's bases for mild steel in 2.0 N HCl at 298 ± 0.1 K.Area of exposure – 7.75 cm²

Time of exposure 19 hrs

x (inhibitor addition)	M (mg) ^Δ	% (y) ^η	$\frac{dx}{=x-\bar{x}}$	$\frac{dy}{=y-\bar{y}}$	$\frac{dx^2}{=(x-\bar{x})^2}$	$\frac{dy^2}{=(y-\bar{y})^2}$	$\frac{dxdy}{=(x-\bar{x})(y-\bar{y})}$
Uninhibited SB ₃	1063	–	–	–	–	–	–
0.12%	110	89.65	–.24	–4.054	.0576	16.434916	.97296
0.24%	99	90.68	–.12	–2.364	.0144	5.588496	.28368
0.36%	88	91.72	0	–0.674	0	.454276	0
0.48%	75	92.94	.12	1.856	.0144	3.444736	.22272
0.60%	51	95.29	.24	5.236	.0576	27.415696	1.25664
Total			0	0	.1440	53.33812	2.736

$$\text{Here, } \bar{x} = \frac{0.180}{5} = 0.36,$$

$$\bar{y} = 92.056$$

$$r = \frac{5 \times 1.6248 - 0}{\sqrt{5 \times 0.144} \sqrt{5 \times 19.03532 - 0}}$$

$$= \frac{8.124}{8.278112853}$$

$$= .981383093$$

$$\cong .98$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The mass loss and percentage inhibition efficiency for 2.0N concentrations of hydrochloric acid and inhibitors are shown in Tables 1-3. It has been observed that the inhibition efficiency increases with increasing concentration of inhibitors.

The maximum inhibition efficiency was obtained for N(anisidine)-1-naphthylimine(SB₃) at an inhibitors concentrate of 0.6% in 2.0 N HCl from the mass loss data it is concluded that the Schiff's base act as a good inhibitor for mild steel in hydrochloric acid.

From the experimental data, it is obvious that the coefficient of correlation between inhibitions addition of SB₁, SB₂ and SB₃ and inhibition efficiency ($\eta\%$) is 0.93, 0.99, and 0.98 respectively. These values of coefficient of correlations indicate that there is a high degree positive correlation between SB₁and $\eta\%$, SB₂and $\eta\%$, and SB₃ and $\eta\%$.

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